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НАУЧНОЕ ОБОСНОВАНИЕ ОРГАНИЗАЦИИ ДЕНТАЛЬНОЙ ПОМОЩИ РАБОТНИКАМ, КОНТАКТИВНЫМ С ЭПОКСИРОВАННОЙ РЕЗИНОЙ

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АННОТАЦИЯ

Целью данного исследования является определение научных основ организации стоматологической помощи персоналу, работающему с эпоксидной смолой. Собраны данные об эпоксидных смолах, их химических свойствах и влиянии на здоровье человека. Проанализированы методы обеспечения стоматологического здоровья сотрудников, профилактики и лечения профессиональных заболеваний. Также даны научные исследования и практические рекомендации по повышению эффективности стоматологических услуг. Результаты исследования имеют важное значение для улучшения условий труда, связанных с эпоксидной смолой, и защиты стоматологического здоровья персонала.

Ключевые слова: эпоксидная смола, стоматологическая помощь, профессиональные заболевания, профилактика, лечение.

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ЕПОКСИД СМОЛАСИ БИЛАН АЛОҚАДА БОЎЛГАН ХОДИМЛАРГА СТОМАТОЛОГИК ЙОРДАМНИ ТАШКИЛ ЕТИШНИ ИЛМИЙ АСОСЛАШ

ANNOTATSIYA

Ushbu tadqiqotning maqsadi epoksid smolasi bilan ishlaydigan xodimlarga stomatologik yordamni tashkil qilishning ilmiy asoslarini aniqlashdir. Epoksid smolalari, ularning kimyoviy xususiyatlari va inson salomatligiga ta'siri borasidagi ma'lumotlar yig'ilgan. Xodimlarning tish salomatligini ta'minlash, kasbga xos kasalliklarning profilaktikasi va davolash usullari tahlil qilingan. Shuningdek, stomatologik xizmatlarning samaradorligini oshirish maqsadida ilmiy tadqiqotlar va amaliy tavsiyalar berilgan. Tadqiqot natijalari, epoksid smolasi bilan bog'liq ish shartlarini yaxshilash va xodimlarning tish salomatligini muhofaza qilishda muhim ahamiyatga ega.

Kalit so'zlar: epoksid smolasi, stomatologik yordam, kasbga xos kasalliklar, profilaktika, davolash.

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SCIENTIFIC JUSTIFICATION OF THE ORGANIZATION OF DENTAL CARE FOR WORKERS IN CONTACT WITH EPOXY RESIN

ANNOTATION

The aim of this study is to determine the scientific basis for the organisation of dental care for personnel working with epoxy resin. Data on epoxy resins, their chemical properties and influence on human health are collected. Methods of providing dental

health care to the staff, prevention and treatment of occupational diseases are analysed. Also scientific research and practical recommendations for improving the efficiency of dental services are given. The results of the study are important for improving epoxy resin-related working conditions and protecting the dental health of staff.

Keywords: epoxy resin, dental care, occupational diseases, prevention, treatment.

Relevance: With the progressive growth of the chemical industry and the extensive chemicalization of multiple areas and branches of the national economy, and the regular introduction into production of various chemical compounds with irritating, toxic, sensitizing, and carcinogenic properties on the body, it is becoming increasingly relevant and very important to study them in more detail.

The properties of epoxy resins are regulated by modification and are the most common additives that are used to improve physical and mechanical properties, "... such as the modulus of elasticity and strength of plastic products. One of the most important applications of epoxy resins is protective coatings, which account for almost 69% of total consumption and in some products can also be used in a decorative function...".¹

In the oral cavity of plastic product workers, chemical compounds as toxic dust can settle as plaque in the area of the necks of the teeth, or through the damaged mucous membrane for faster penetration and absorption, which causes serious consequences in the form of periodontitis, stomatitis.

The harm caused by chemicals to certain organs depends on the amount (dose) of these chemicals absorbed by the body. Inflammatory diseases, as well as periodontal damage, have an etiological connection with a violation of the microbiocenosis of the oral cavity. The constant influence of chemical compounds in low concentrations in the air and on the oral mucosa can contribute to a change in the composition of saliva and the structure of microbiocenosis, which ultimately leads to a secondary deterioration in the hygienic condition of the oral cavity.

The high prevalence, tendency to progression, and multifaceted effects on both the dental system and the body as a whole, as well as ambiguous treatment approaches, make periodontal diseases one of the most problematic nosologies in modern medicine. The conducted studies "... have reliably established that the dependence of the health status of the population on the effects of chemical factors leads to the fact that environmental pollution leads to the development of adverse health consequences, expressed in mortality, morbidity, deterioration of physical development, widespread premorbid conditions ...". Today, a wide range of scientific research is being conducted aimed at improving methods of diagnosis, treatment and prevention in the early stages of diseases caused by industrial conditions that affect the qualitative and quantitative parameters of oral fluid, that is, volume, mineral composition and protective properties of pH.

The object of the study was 2 groups of patients.

Group 1 (main group) 75 workers with chronic generalized periodontitis among the employees of Optima Best Plast LLC, Polyplast.

Group 2 – (control) 65 workers who have no contact with epoxy resin.

Subject of the study: oral fluid, 140 of the OHIP-49-RU quality of life questionnaire, epidemiological examination cards for workers to determine dental indicators.

Research methods. To achieve the goal and objectives, the following methods were applied: epidemiological, clinical and dental, immunological, and statistical.

The scientific novelty of the research is as follows:

- data on the dental status of workers in the production of epoxy resin at the Optima Best Plast LLC, Polyplast plant were obtained;

The purpose of the study: to increase the effectiveness of comprehensive treatment and prevention of periodontal diseases in workers, taking into account the peculiarities of their exposure to epoxy resin.

Research objectives:

- to study the dental status of workers exposed to epoxy resin;
- to determine the state of nonspecific resistance of the body and local immunity of the oral cavity in workers exposed to epoxy resin.

- to identify the adsorption activity of microorganisms by epithelial cells in workers exposed to epoxy resin.

- to study the impact of dental health of workers exposed to epoxy resin on the quality of life according to the OHIP-49-RU index.

- to evaluate the effectiveness of a complex of therapeutic and preventive measures for workers with chronic generalized periodontitis in production with exposure to epoxy resin

- it was revealed that there is a violation of adaptive mechanisms in the oral fluid at critical concentrations of lysozyme, S-IgA and the development of clinical signs of immunodeficiency;

- the indicators of the quality of life of workers in the production of plastic products according to the OHIP-49-RU index were studied and the influence of dental health on it was determined.;

- as a result of the conducted research, a set of measures will be developed aimed at the prevention and treatment of chronic periodontitis among workers in the production of plastic products and its effectiveness will be evaluated.

A comprehensive dental examination of 140 main workshops was carried out. Of these, 75 are those working in molding shops in contact with epoxy resin – the main group that does not have contact with epoxy resin – the control group is 65 workers (30 people in the workshop for laying out finished products, 35 people in the workshop for repairing equipment), aged 25 to 55 years, who were divided into three periods of service:

- 1 - workers with up to 5 years of experience.

- 2 - workers with 5 to 10 years of experience.

- 3 - workers with more than 10 years of experience.

Generally accepted classifications were used in the diagnosis of major diseases, assessment of their severity and prevalence.

The examination of the oral cavity was carried out on the basis of WHO recommendations. The epidemiological survey card included questionnaire data on the indices of oral hygiene and periodontal diseases (indices. KPU, OHIS, Green-Vermilion Index, 1964), CPITN, PI (Russell A., 1956), RMA (Parma C, 1960).

The impact of dental morbidity on the quality of life of workers was assessed using a special dental questionnaire - OHIP-49-RU. The Russian-language version of the questionnaire "Dental Health Impact Profile" OHIP-49-RU (G.M.Barer, 2006) was used, which contains 49 questions divided into 7 main blocks: physical discomfort and pain (PD), limitation of function (OP), psychological discomfort (PD),

social maladjustment (SD), physical and psychological disability (FN and PN) and damage (U).

Statistical processing of the obtained results was carried out by the method of variation statistics. The reliability of the differences was assessed using the Student's criterion within 95% confidence ($p < 0.05$).

In the third chapter of the dissertation "Assessment of the working conditions of workers with epoxy resin", the hygienic condition of the working area of enterprises is assessed. The studies were taken on the basis of hygienic data from the laboratory of the sanitary and epidemiological surveillance station, taken from the LLC over the past five years.

Optima Best Plast and Polyplast LLC, operating in the Samarkand region, includes a number of main and auxiliary facilities, including workshops for the production of plastic products made from epoxy resin, where work is carried out through a continuous technological cycle, not only a high level of automation, remote control, but also manually, where molding is carried out., painting and laying of plastic products.

It should be noted that harmful substances of hazard class 2-4, which are part of the epoxy resin (epichlorohydrin, toluene, definyolpropane, caustic soda, dimethylaniline, etc.), including flammable, volatile, explosive substances, which under certain conditions can enter the air of the working area, circulate in the technological flow of production (Table 1).

Table 1

Pollution of the working area air by harmful substances

Chemical compounds	Production, workshop				MPC (mg/m3)	Hazard class
	The shape of the brewhouse	epoxy resin heating workshop	paint and varnish workshop	warehous use of finished products		
	Concentration in the working area (mg/m3)					
Epichlorohydrin	1,8±0,03	1,9±0,03	1,3±0,03	0,4±0,03	1,0	II
	1,2±0,04	1,3±0,04	0,6±0,04	-	0,5	IY
Toluene	6,7±0,04	7,2±0,04	5,3±0,00	3,2±0,00	5,0	III
Diphenylolpropane	0,9±0,00	1,2±0,03	0,6±0,04	0,1±0,04	0,5	II

In addition, the industries use powerful equipment that is a source of noise (compressors, pumps). The need for periodic stay of workers in outdoor installations determines the effect of low air temperatures, wind, and precipitation on them during the cold season.

Thus, the use of continuous technologies, high-performance equipment, complex automation and mechanization of technological processes in the production of plastic products does not exclude the possibility of exposure to the body of workers to a complex of harmful chemical (harmful substances) and physical (industrial noise, unfavorable microclimate) factors, as well as factors of the labor process (hard work, labor intensity, manual molding, warming up the resin).

One of the main unfavorable factors is the heating microclimate. Sources of heat generation are melting vessels emitting thermal energy and heated surfaces of equipment.

The fourth chapter of the dissertation "The state of dental morbidity of plastic products manufacturing workers" presents the results of their own research. When studying the indicators of the OHI-S index, the level of oral hygiene among workers in contact with epoxy resin in the group with up to 5 years of experience was 1.93 ± 0.24 (high), in the group with 5 to 10 years of experience - 2.4 ± 0.07 and in the group with more than 10 years of experience - 2.8 ± 0.43 (very high) ($p < 0.05$). The level of oral hygiene was assessed as unsatisfactory in the group with up to 5 years of experience, and poor in the groups with higher experience, while maintaining differences in indicators of oral hygiene among workers in the main and control groups. Thus, the level of oral hygiene was assessed as unsatisfactory both among workers of harmful industries and in the control group

Figure 1. The value of the OHI-S index in plastic production workers and in the control group, depending on the length of service.

In the group with up to 5 years of experience, workers in contact with epoxy resin had a CPI index of 15.2 ± 0.54 , which is 1.2 times more than in the control group with the same work experience. In the group with experience from 5 to 10 years, there was an increase in intensity among both workers in the main and control groups. The highest level of dental caries intensity was observed in the group with more than 10 years of experience. The increase in intensity compared with the group with experience up to 5 years was 1.5 ± 0.5 , with the group with

experience from 5 to 10 years - 0.9 ± 0.3 . The control group also showed an increase in the incidence of dental caries in the group with more than 10 years of experience: compared with the group of workers with up to 5 years of experience - 1.3 ± 0.5 , and in the group with experience from 5 to 10 years - 0.5 ± 0.3 . Thus, workers in contact with epoxy resin have more a marked increase in the intensity of dental caries and these data correlate with the indicators in the control group ($p < 0.05$)

(Fig. 3).

Figure 3. The intensity of dental caries (KPU index) among workers in the production of plastic products, depending on the length of service

When assessing periodontal tissue inflammation (PMA) in the group of workers with up to 5 years of experience, we determined a mild degree of inflammation in $47.2 \pm 0.04\%$, in the group with 5 to 10 years of experience - in $24.2 \pm 0.41\%$, in the group with more than 10 years of experience - in $2.5 \pm 0.03\%$. As the length of service increased, there was an increase in the degree of inflammation in periodontal tissues. Thus, in the group with up to 5 years of experience, a mild degree of inflammation was diagnosed in $48.6 \pm 0.14\%$, an average degree of $3.7 \pm 0.05\%$ (localized form). In the group with experience from 5 to 10 years, a mild degree of inflammation was detected in $67.3 \pm 0.30\%$, the average degree was $8.8 \pm 0.26\%$. In the group with more than 10 years of experience, mild inflammation was more often diagnosed - in $61.4 \pm 0.40\%$ of those examined, however, the average degree of inflammation in this group was diagnosed much more often - in $20.8 \pm 0.35\%$.

The results of our research show that almost 100% of those examined need treatment for periodontal diseases, which is confirmed by the definition of the CPITN index.

When examining the component of the CPITN-TN index (treatment need - indicates the necessary medical procedures), we found that the specific

The weight of the TN1 component (oral hygiene instruction) prevails in the control group, TN2 and TN3 in workers in contact with epoxy resin. That is, there are more people in the group exposed to harmful industrial factors who need more qualified assistance. In such groups, in addition to teaching rational oral hygiene, comprehensive treatment is required with the involvement of related specialists.

In the production of plastic products, in the main group with up to 5 years of work experience, the percentage of healthy sextants was $5.3 \pm 0.23\%$, in the group with 5 to 10 years of work experience - $4.2 \pm 0.34\%$, in the group with more than 10 years of experience - $3.5 \pm 0.26\%$. In the control group, among people with work experience of up to 5 years, it was $19.6 \pm 1.4\%$, for those working from 5 to 10 years - $15.7 \pm 2.21\%$, in the group with more than 10 years of experience - $11.8 \pm 1.43\%$ of the surveyed ($p < 0.05$) (Fig.4).

Figure 4. The level of healthy sextants according to the CPITN index among groups of workers, depending on work experience

When studying the structure of the index of need for treatment of periodontal diseases, the most frequently diagnosed sign is a periodontal pocket 4-5 mm deep, while we noted that with an increase in work experience in hazardous production,

there was an increase in the prevalence of this indicator (Fig.5.). So in the group with up to 5 years of experience among workers in contact with epoxy resin The periodontal pocket from 4 to 5 mm was determined with resin in $48.6 \pm 2.6\%$ of the examined, in the

group with experience from 5 to 10 years - $67.3 \pm 2.1\%$, and in the group with experience of more than 10 years in $61.2 \pm 2.3\%$ of cases.

Figure 5. The prevalence of a periodontal pocket with a depth of 4 to 5 mm among the groups, depending on work experience

The intensity of the developed, pronounced type of periodontal tissue pathology per examinee was constantly increasing (Fig.6): in workers in contact with epoxy resin, from 1.9 ± 0.05 in the group with up to 5 years of experience, to

2.8 ± 0.03 in the group with more than 10 years of experience. In the control group, the intensity of this trait increased from 0.6 ± 0.03 to 1.6 ± 0.05 .

Figure 6. Intensity of the periodontal pocket feature with a depth of 4 to 5 mm per surveyed worker group, depending on work experience

In workers who had been in contact with epoxy resin for up to 5 years, hard dental deposits were found in $38.5 \pm 2.2\%$ of cases. This is 2.33 times more than in the group with 5 to 10 years of experience and 3.3 times more than in workers with more than 10 years of experience.

The intensity of the tartar deposition process decreased from 1.32 ± 0.03 (in the group with up to 5 years of experience) to 0.5 ± 0.04 (in the group with more than 10 years of experience) (Fig. 7).

In the control group, tartar was detected in $34.2 \pm 2.3\%$ in the group with up to 5 years of experience, in $27.8 \pm 1.2\%$ in the group with 5 to 10 years of experience, and in $22.6 \pm 3.3\%$ ($p < 0.05$). The number of segments with tartar per examinee in these groups was 2.16 ± 0.05 and 1.38 ± 0.05 , respectively.

Conclusion. Based on the results of the dissertation of the Doctor of Philosophy in Medical Sciences (PhD) on the topic

"Scientific justification of the organization of dental care for workers in contact with epoxy resin", the following conclusions were presented:

1. Among workers in the main specialties exposed to epoxy resin in the manufacture of plastic products, the average OHI-S index was higher than in the control group and amounted to 2.38 ± 0.32 , a high prevalence and intensity of major dental diseases were identified: the CPI index averaged 17.7 ± 1.44 , the prevalence of periodontal tissue diseases was $94.5 \pm 2.34\%$.

2. The level of sIgA in the oral fluid of workers in contact with epoxy resin exceeded this indicator in the control group by an average of 4.3 times. We have identified a tendency to increase the sIgA content in the oral fluid in people with up to 5 years of work experience, with a gradual decrease in this indicator in groups with higher work experience.

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